
The vasoconstrictor endothelin system involvement in chronic kidney diseases pathogenesis is now the most often employed treatment method

Moataz Dowaidar^{1,2}

¹Department of Bioengineering, King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals (KFUPM), Dhahran 31261, Saudi Arabia

²Interdisciplinary Research Center for Hydrogen and Energy Storage (IRC-HES), King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals (KFUPM), Dhahran, 31261, Saudi Arabia.

Abstract: Over 30,000 publications have been published about the vasoconstrictor endothelin-1, which was identified by Yanagisawa and co-workers in 1988. While the evidence is quite compelling, scientists can only speculate on how the endothelin (ET) system affects blood pressure and renal function at this time. ET system involvement in chronic kidney diseases (CKD) pathogenesis is now the most often employed treatment method. ET1, ET2, and ET3 are all members of the endothelin family. Endothelium, renal, and smooth muscle cells all generate ET-1, a significant isoform found in both cardiovascular and renal systems. Kidney cells act on, and contain, ET-1. The ETA receptor is found in the brain and medulla, but not in the vasa recta or glomeruli. Epithelial and endothelial cells contain the ETB receptor, which is most prominent in collecting duct cells. 3 In several experiments, ET-1 has been established to be largely a preglomerular vasoconstrictor. Mesangial proliferation, contraction, and collagen production are regulated by ET-1 and ETB receptors in podocytes. The epithelium in the collecting duct cells in the medulla is important in controlling Na excretion and BP. Without the ET-1 gene, the mice have hypertension and reduced natriuresis in response to salt loading. Et-1, ETB receptor, and hypertension are shown in mice that have lost the ETB receptor gene. There is no correlation between blood pressure regulation and natriuresis. Combined disruption of the ETA and ETB receptors has greater effects on blood pressure and Na reabsorption than when ETB receptor activity is missing. It appears that the ETB receptor doesn't work until ETB is present. Collecting duct-derived ET receptors reduces the transport of sodium. Src kinase and MAPK1/2 decrease epidermal Na channel (ENaC) function, decreasing water and salt reabsorption. Moreover, inner medullary collecting duct cells and vasa recta-bearing cells will release NO, which decreases sodium transport.

1. Introduction

Endothelin-1, the most potent known vasoconstrictor in humans, has been investigated in over 30,000 papers since it was discovered by Yanagisawa and co-workers in 1988. Evidence clearly suggests that the ET system regulates blood pressure and kidney function, controlling blood flow, glomerular hemodynamics, sodium/water balance, and acid-base balance. The ET system is implicated in the pathophysiology of cardiovascular and chronic kidney diseases (CKD), which is presently the most often utilized therapeutic strategy.

In this review, we briefly summarize the biology of the ET system in the vasculature and in the kidney, and offer the rationale for ET receptor antagonism in clinical renal disorders. Finally, we assess the potential of utilizing a multipharmac strategy, including inhibition of ET and RAS, in patients with CKD.

The ET system's biology

2. The kidney's ET system

Three distinct peptides—ET1, ET2, and ET3—all coded by three unique genes, are part of the endothelin family. The major isoform in the cardiovascular and renal systems is ET-1, which binds to two G protein-coupled ET type-A (ETA) and type-B (ETB) receptors produced by distinct cell types, including endothelium and smooth muscle cells, fibroblasts, and renal cells.

Kidney cells both contain, and act on, ET-1 (3, 7). Rather, the ETA receptor is expressed in the brain and medulla, but not in the vasa recta or glomeruli (8). The ETB receptor, on the other hand, is found on endothelial and epithelial cells, and is heavily prevalent in collecting duct cells. (3) In a number of experimental conditions, ET-1 has been demonstrated to be predominantly a preglomerular vasoconstrictor (10). Podocytes generate a higher amount of glomerular ET-1 than does the mesangium, and that ET-1 controls mesangial proliferation, contraction, and collagen formation via ETA and ETB receptors. ET-1, which is produced in the collecting duct cells in the medulla, has a major role in regulating Na excretion and BP (13). Mice lacking the ET-1 gene (and hence the collecting duct) experience hypertension and attenuated natriuresis in response to salt loading (14,15,16). In mice with the ETB receptor gene deletion, elevated BP and Na intake were detected, as well as a natriuretic action mediated by ET-1 through the ETB receptor (18). BP control and natriuresis are not clearly linked to the ductal ETA receptor (19). Combined disruption of ETA and ETB receptors has higher effects on blood pressure and Na reabsorption than in animals lacking just the collecting duct-specific ETB receptor (20). According to these findings, without the ETB receptor, the ETA receptor might be doing more than it typically does. Partially, collecting duct-derived ET receptors inhibits the transfer of sodium. Epithelial Na channel (ENaC) activity is rapidly reduced, hence lowering water and salt reabsorption, using Src kinase and MAPK1/2 as well as ET-1. Moreover, ETA and ETB receptor engagement in inner medullary collecting duct cells and vasa recta causes the generation of nitric oxide (NO) that suppresses Na transport (22, 23).

3. ET and RAS crosstalk

RAS controls renal function via several commonalities and complicated interactions with the ET. The RAS system is found in all renal compartments and cell types. Mesangial contraction, proliferation, and matrix creation are all associated with ANG II and ET-1. Et-1 secretion is stimulated by ANG II, which perpetuates the cycle. ANG II also has part of its effects mediated via ET-1. ANG II infusion leads to vascular and renal ET-1 production in rats, and ETA-selective antagonism prevents the hypertensive response, which is caused by ANG II, in experimental models and in healthy humans. Also, ET-1 increases aldosterone production by the zona glomerulosa (30). With renin hypertension, ETA and ETB receptor antagonism decreases plasma aldosterone levels and decreases BP.

4. The ET-1 in renal disorders

In proteinuria-associated chronic nephropathies, increases in renal ET-1 expression are often seen. The first study demonstrating the renoprotective impact of blocking ETA receptors was conducted in rats in 1993 (36). Extensive pre-clinical evidence suggests that ET-1, primarily via the ETA receptor, is involved in the etiology of CKD in both hypertensive and normotensive settings (2, 37, 38). Albumin overload of proximal tubular cells increases the levels of ET-1, which is discharged to the basolateral side of the cells. In vivo, ET-1 might contribute to tubulointerstitial inflammation and fibrosis (7). Glomerular injury and increasing renal failure are associated with podocyte dysfunction. Due to increased plasma proteins,

TGF β , and complement proteins, ET-1 gene expression in glomerular damage cells increases. Because podocyte ET-1 release follows, podocyte structure and function deteriorate because of an autocrine process. Podocyte-derived ET-1 is also associated with nephrin downregulation and podocyte shedding (40). Additionally, ET-1 promotes an epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition-like phenotype, which results in enhanced motility, cell retraction, and intercellular gaps, processes that enhance protein permeability across the glomerular filter (39, 41, 42, 43).

5. kidney-related genetic illnesses

polycystic kidney disease

ADPKD is the most common kind of hereditary kidney disease, and it is the most common cause of ESRD in the United States. Current medications target hypertension, pain, and chronic renal disease, but fail to delay or prevent the development of ESRD. Polycystin-1 and polycystin-2 mutations induce aberrant tubular cell proliferation, fluid secretion, extracellular matrix production, angiogenesis, and cilia-mediated mechanosensation, which leads to the creation of numerous renal epithelial cysts. SNPs in the EDN1 and EDNRA (ETA receptor) genes have been shown to alter renal disease progression towards ESRD in ADPKD. First in vitro observations revealed that ET-1 has a direct mitogenic and profibrotic action on renal tubular cells (48, 49). Elevated plasma ET-1 levels, as well as ET-1, cyclic AMP, and EGF have been reported in human and experimental ADPKD (50, 51).

ET-1 transgenic mice with ADPKD develop interstitial fibrosis, glomerulosclerosis, and cerebral cysts (52). With long-term treatment of selective ETA receptor antagonists (LU135252 or darusentan), there was an increase in kidney weight and cyst number, but inhibition of ETA/ETB receptors prevented these adverse effects. In response to the specific ETA receptor antagonist atrasentan, similar effects were seen on tubular cell proliferation and cyst-phenotype homogeneity (51). Despite this, ETB receptor antagonists aggravated cystic kidney disease, which was corrected by combining ETA/ETB receptor inhibition (51). Results from this study reveal that ETB and ETA receptor levels are not balanced in ADPKD, which might contribute to the course of the disease.

6. Alport syndrome

Alport syndrome (AS) is a disease characterized by glomerular nephropathy with hematuria, leading to ESRD (54). Changes in the genes encoding for the three collagen isotypes — $\alpha 3$ (IV), $\alpha 4$ (IV), and $\alpha 5$ (IV) — lead to structural abnormalities such as uneven thinning and thickening of the GBM and to podocyte invasion into the GBM and foot process effacement (55). Mesangial cells have recently been implicated in the pathogenesis of Alport glomerular disease (56). With increasing blood pressure, glomerular endothelial cells generate ectopic laminin isoform and $\alpha 1\alpha 2\alpha 1$ (IV) collagen to meet the demand (57). Ectopic extracellular matrix protein synthesis stimulates the expression of proinflammatory cytokines and matrix metalloproteases in podocytes, accelerating disease development (57). Alport mice treated with atrasentan display significant reductions in proteinuria and normalization of glomerular GBM shape and GSS (57).

7. Hemolytic anemia

Chronic erythrocyte sickling and hemolysis results in tissue ischemia, increasing glomerulopathy, and hematuria (58). There is evidence that the EDN1 gene variation is related to vaso-occlusive crises in SCD patients (59). Although initial research showed that bosentan treatment provided SCD mice with protection against vascular congestion and

inflammation, newer studies indicate that unselective ETA/B receptor antagonist has limited benefits, indicating that ETA receptor antagonism with hydroxyurea is the most effective way to treat renal disease progression.

8. fSGL

FSGS is a complex set of diseases that contribute to glomerular dysfunction in people who frequently develop nephrotic syndrome and proteinuria. A mutation was found in over 20 genes, including the slit diaphragm and actin cytoskeleton in the podocyte. Cumulative clinical and experimental evidence suggests that ET-1 may be involved in the disease's etiology (64, 65). The many insults to podocytes result in wide-ranging morphological alterations, including hypertrophy, foot process effacement, and separation from the GBM (66).

In aging-associated FSGS, therapy with an ETA receptor antagonist inhibits the senescence-related increase in p21, a cell-cycle inhibitor implicated in both aging and differentiation. The selective ETA receptor antagonist sitaxsentan is able to reduce podocyte loss and glomerular damage in the adriamycin-treated FSGS model. Alterations in podocyte-endothelial interaction led to the evolution of FSGS. ETS-1, produced from defective podocytes, has a paracrine impact on endothelial cells and accelerates the onset of FSGS in two distinct animal models (68). Similarly, podocyte-derived ET-1 causes the breakdown of endothelial glycocalyx, which precedes the establishment of glomerular histopathological abnormalities in adriamycin nephropathy (69).

9. Glomerulonephritis

Renal lupus

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is most often associated with kidney damage caused by immune complex deposit or activation of the complement system (70). Anti-endothelial cell antibodies and immune complexes produced from SLE patients' sera can promote ET-1 production from endothelial cells, suggesting that ET-1 may be involved in glomerular vascular damage (71). A large, cohort research comprising 132 participants with CKD discovered that urine ET-1 levels increased in individuals with SLE, even when their GFR was normal (72). Giant mesangial cell proliferation and matrix generation is associated with the presence of ET-1 in SLE patients (73, 74). Renal ET-1 and ETB receptors are present in NZB/WF1 mice (34). Notably, ETA receptor antagonist-treated patients had significantly reduced renal matrix buildup, proteinuria, and hypertension (75).

Asbestosis

The probability of development to ESRD within one year is much greater with mesangial proliferative IgA nephropathy than with normal intrarenal ET-1 (76). Although GG4A Haplotype of the EDN1 Gene was connected with IgA Nephropathy, ET-1 Gene Polymorphisms Studies to Demonstrate Correlations have Failed (77) IgA nephropathy patients with high-grade proteinuria tend to have robust renal expression of ET-1 and ETB receptor in the proximal tubules and glomeruli. Neutrophils from individuals with IgA nephropathy increased ET-1 synthesis by mesangial cells in vitro, indicating that glomerular neutrophil infiltration occurring in this disease may contribute to inflammation (79). Little is known about the ET-antagonism renoprotection in experimental IgA nephropathy. Although FR139317 is an effective selective ETA receptor antagonist for IgA nephropathy, because of the paucity of a decent model of IgA nephropathy, no more analysis has been done.

Treatments with RAS antagonists and the special combination needed with ACE inhibitors are highly successful in slowing renal disease development owing to their influence on systemic and glomerular hypertension and protein ultrafiltration. While ACE inhibitors can slow renal disease development, therapy must be begun early. Recent evidence indicates that combined inhibition of the RAS and ET systems is a unique treatment strategy that will improve the protective effects of RAS inhibition.

10. Nephrotic Syndrome

This notion was first theorized in the late 1990s. In the model of idiopathic membranous nephropathy with increased tubular ET-1 expression, ACE inhibitor trandolapril, or selective ETA receptor antagonist LU-135252 given alone could significantly reduce BP, but a combination of treatment yielded better renal function and reduced glomerular alterations (82). The findings with the Ren-2 transgenic rats later verified the relevance of this multidrug strategy. To a larger degree, in this paradigm, combined RAS and ETA receptor blockage soon after renal mass ablation improves survival, proteinuria, and glomerular damage (83). ACE inhibitor and LU-135252 treatment reduced both glomerulosclerosis and tubular interstitial damage, but didn't improve urine protein excretion. The RAS/ET-1 blocker has an advantage if administered before other RAS inhibition (because atrasentan's efficacy did not improve renal function in a model with preexisting CKD).

11. Diabetic kidney disease

Type 2 diabetes is the most common form of diabetes and, thus, the major cause of ESRD. Studies in experimental type 1 and type 2 diabetes have demonstrated that there is a link between ET-1 levels and increasing glomerular damage, extracellular matrix deposition, and renal fibrosis. Multiple investigations in diabetic rats have proven the usefulness of dual ETA/B receptor inhibition, which normalizes renal function because of its capacity to lower oxidative stress in response to elevated ET-1 levels (89, 90). Selective ETA antagonist, avosentan, attenuates renal functional degradation and structural damage, including glomerulosclerosis, macrophage infiltration, oxidative stress, and diabetes-associated atherosclerosis, in an accelerated diabetic nephropathy model (91) Streptozotocin injection into rats decreases renal synthesis of inflammatory mediators and prevents microalbuminuria. A more recent study demonstrated positive benefits of atrasentan on the development of renal damage and hemodynamics throughout the latter stages of CKD in type 1 and type 2 diabetes. ETA receptor blockage protects the glomerulus largely because it limits podocyte loss, a common hallmark of overt diabetes. Previous research has provided support for the significance of both ETA and ETB receptors in triggering podocyte dysfunction in response to ET-1 (95). Both hyperglycemia and ET-1 are proven to produce podocyte cytoskeleton breakdown, changes in nephrin expression, podocyte detachment, and death (43, 96).

The combination of the ETA receptor antagonist avosentan with the ACE inhibitor lisinopril brings renoprotection to type 1 diabetic rats toward the end of the disease (94). Although monotherapy only partially improves renal function, the combination recovers proteinuria, restores podocyte quantity, and even regresses glomerular lesions (94).

Additionally, dual therapy also protects against tubulointerstitial injury. Because ACE inhibition increases glomerular permselectivity while ETA inhibition reduces the deleterious effect of protein absorption by proximal tubular cells, reducing tubular interstitial inflammation, fibrosis, and peritubular capillary abnormalities (94), concurrent inhibition of the ET-1 and ANG II pathways provides significant renoprotection, and the combination treatment

exemplifies this. Although dual RAS/ET-1 blockage is less efficient than ACE inhibition, combination treatment gives higher protection against tubulointerstitial damage, according to studies from the Amann group (98).

12. Patients with hypertension and/or chronic renal disease

A search for a solution to resistant hypertension and/or CKD has been made more urgent than ever before. Some of this anticipation is due to the abundance of pre-clinical data and positive findings from earlier clinical trials (although not without some safety signals as will be discussed below). We've done extensive research in the past, and the present situation is covered as well.

13. Resistance to high blood pressure

Resistant hypertension, defined as the concurrent use of 3 distinct classes of antihypertensive medications, occurs in around 25% of patients. The most recent important research using ETA/B receptor antagonists was DORADO, in which darusentan was delivered to patients with type 2 diabetes and kidney disease. Darusentan showed better efficacy than placebo, with a systolic and diastolic blood pressure (BP) reduction of ~9/5 mm Hg and the incidence of fluid-retaining events around the same. DORADO-AC compared darusentan with guanfacine, a central α -2 adrenoreceptor agonist, in 1453 patients with resistant hypertension. While sitting BP (primary endpoint) was lowered by darusentan to a larger extent than guanfacine, the placebo group exhibited a considerable BP decline and substantial darusentan vs. guanfacine differences. Even though darusentan lowered ambulatory BP more than guanfacine or placebo, but was not able to satisfy the primary endpoint, the darusentan program was discontinued. The sponsor's latest study discovered that while an ETA/B receptor antagonist (aprocritantan) reduces systolic BP, fluid retention was not a significant concern in 490 individuals with essential hypertension. Phase 3 clinical research has been launched in 600 patients with resistant hypertension with a main endpoint of change in seated office systolic BP after 4 weeks of therapy, followed by an additional 32 weeks to measure medication durability (Phase 3, projected completion date in 2021). Of note, the greater dosage of aprocritantan administered in the first 4-week period and in all patients in the extension period was observed to raise plasma ET-1 levels, probably by inhibiting ETB receptors. Additionally, PRECISION might face challenges over which BP monitoring is used (use of office BP instead of ambulatory despite the issues with DORADO-AC). Aprocritantan is an ET receptor antagonist, and it is also teratogenic, which means that it may cause birth defects in females.

14. Diabetes and kidney disease

In the first large trial, avosentan, a non-selective ETA/B receptor antagonist, was used for type 2 diabetes and CKD. After 12 weeks in 286 individuals with type 2 diabetes on RAS blockade with a GFR of ~80 ml/min/1.73 m², avosentan reduced urine albumin excretion by around 30%. A second piece of research discovered that avosentan dosage depends on the patient and indicated that avosentan should be taken at levels of around 5 mg per day (105). ASCEND was a phase 3 study that evaluated the effect of avosentan on renal disease development in 1392 type 2 diabetic individuals with stages 2–4 CKD (eGFR 33 ml/min/1.73m²). At 4 months, Avosentan lowered the UACR by 35% over placebo. However, due to fluid retention, especially owing to threefold increases in the frequency of congestive heart failure, the experiment was prematurely stopped. It is clear in retrospect that the ASCEND dosages were higher than intended; also, the inadequate selection of patients, and requiring diuretic usage were probably causes of the adverse event.

Studies utilizing atrasentan, an ETA receptor-selective antagonist, began following the ASCEND discovery. Patients with type 2 diabetes on maximum tolerated labeled doses (MTLD) of a RAS inhibitor, atrasentan at the 0.75 and 1.75 mg levels, had a ~30% reduction in UACR compared to patients on placebo (10). MTLD of RAS inhibitors, with eGFR of 30–75 ml/min/1.73m² and UACR of 300–3500 mg/g (RADAR), atrasentan (0.75 or 1.25 mg/day) decreased UACR by around 36% at either dosage (107). Peripheral edema occurrences showed no change regardless of whether or not patients had a history of heart failure, a high dosage loop diuretic treatment, or an increased BNP level. Finally, the drug achieved this goal, regardless of whether the patients were on statins.

RADAR supported the start of a phase 3 study of diabetic nephropathy in persons with eGFR 25–75 ml/min/1.73 m² and a UACR of 300–5000 mg/g who were using MTLD or RAS blockers, along with a diuretic (unless it was not tolerated). A total of 5,117 individuals were administered atrasentan (0.75 mg/day) for 6 weeks. The responders (n=2648) saw a UACR decline of at least 30%, whereas the non-responders (the initial group of 1,020 patients detected) had a smaller UACR decline. Those who responded and those who did not were given atrasentan (0.75 mg/day) or placebo, and the study participants were all kept in the dark about their assignment. After final patient data collection, it was evident that atrasentan decreased renal events in responders (79 of 1325 patients in the atrasentan group and 105 of 1323 in the placebo group after a median follow-up of 2.2 years, hazard ratio (HR) 0.65 (95% CI 0.49–0.88); p = 0.0047). Fluid retention-related adverse events were more common in the atrasentan group, and hospitalization for heart failure was more common, though not statistically significant (3.5% vs. 2.6% of responders, respectively, HR 1.33 (95% CI 0.85–2.07); p = 0.208). Atrasentan did not affect composite cardiovascular outcomes, but it did lower nonfatal stroke. Atrasentan failed to substantially change the primary composite renal outcome in non-responders (event rate: 73/509 in the atrasentan group and 87/511 in the placebo group, HR 0.75 (95% CI 0.55–1.03); p = 0.079).

SONAR offers numerous key lessons. First, atrasentan lowers renal events in type 2 diabetes. These studies provide proof of concept, the first of their kind in nearly two decades. Also, SONAR is the first big renal study to adopt a customized medicine strategy, concentrating on enhancing effectiveness and safety. Third, constant attention to fluid retention is still required in patients using ET receptor antagonists. Finally, combining an ET receptor antagonist and an SGLT2 inhibitor could yield an additive or synergistic renoprotection due to the powerful diuretic impact of the SGLT2 inhibitor.

15. Kidney disorders are not associated with diabetes.

Numerous forms of renal disease now may be treated using ET receptor antagonists. These tests include experiments done on patients with primary FSGS, IgA nephropathy, and sickle cell disease.

A phase 2 randomized double-blind experiment (DUET) was undertaken utilizing a substituted N-3-isoxazolyl biphenylsulfonamide, called sparsentan, in 109 individuals with primary FSGS. The use of sparsentan or irbesartan varied based on the patients' age from 8 to 75 years, as well as their eGFR, with or without proteinuria. Sparsentan (pooled for analysis) caused a bigger reduction in the urine protein/creatinine ratio (UPCR) than irbesartan (45% versus 19%, p < 0.006) and likewise lowered BP at the higher dosages. Treatment-emergent edema was observed in 12.3% of sparsentan patients (all dosages combined), but only 2.8% of irbesartan patients had fluid retention. The study power was insufficient to detect

differences in sparsentan efficacy or safety; however, no significant differences were found. A factor in this study was the inclusion of youngsters. Pre-clinical research suggests that ET receptor antagonism may induce gonadal damage (see below). This matter remains open, but very significant. Finally, serum albumin was normal in individuals in DUET, which raises the question of whether ET receptor blocking may have different consequences in more severe nephrotic disease (related to perhaps less protein-bound drug or differences in fluid retention). There is no literature on this subject, hence research into this population must account for these special challenges.

The DUPLEX clinical study, which began in individuals with biopsy-proven primary FSGS, was successful. A total of 300 patients, aged 8–75, with an eGFR > 30 ml/min/1.73 m² and > 1.5 g of proteinuria will be randomized to sparsentan (the maximum dosage in DUET) or irbesartan. The slope of eGFR over 2 years and the proportion of patients obtaining a UPCR ≤ 1.5 g/g and a $> 40\%$ decrease from baseline in UPCR are the key objectives. Estimated completion date: 2022. Taking this into perspective, a reduction in proteinuria may make nephrotic syndrome less severe, paving the way for an indication that is not initially dependent on showing GFR decrease and/or ESRD.

A phase 3 study, PROTECT, is assessing the nephroprotective effects of ETA receptor antagonism in IgA nephropathy. 280 patients, all biopsy-proven IgA nephropathy patients with eGFR < 30 ml/min/1.73 m² and > 1 g of proteinuria, will be randomly assigned to either sparseafor (up-titrated to 400 mg/day) or irbesartan and followed for 2 years. The primary outcome will be change from baseline in UPCR at week 36, while secondary outcomes will measure change in eGFR. The completion date is 2023.

An exciting phase 1 trial utilizing an ETA/B receptor antagonist called ambrisentan is under way in sickle cell disease (113). In addition to safety and tolerability, critical secondary objectives will include renal function (eGFR and albuminuria/proteinuria) and nociception/pain.

16. Endothelin receptor antagonist side effects

RAS inhibitors are all prohibited in pregnancy due to teratogenic effects (114). In animals, bosentan causes lower sperm counts and testicular atrophy, while the effect on testicular function has not been observed in people (for pulmonary hypertension). Toxicity to the liver has been recorded, particularly with larger dosages of sulfonamide-based ET receptor antagonists. However, these more recent dosing approaches have avoided such issues (115-267).

The main difficulty with antagonists for the ETA receptor in studies is fluid retention. After initiating medication, hemodilutional anemia (a fast increase in the hematocrit) and edema are frequently observed. Most likely, these processes are due to blockage of ET-1-induced natriuresis and diuresis in the collecting duct as well as probable effects on vascular permeability (18). Residual fluid retention occurs with either ETA-selective or ETA/B receptor antagonists; the causes of fluid retention are not well understood. Preliminary ET receptor blocker trials reported considerable fluid retention caused by excessive dose, suboptimal patient selection, and insufficient diuretics. SONAR, meant to promote efficacy and safety, increased (albeit not significantly) adverse events due to fluid retention. However, this does not indicate that ET receptor blockers are doomed as therapeutic agents in CKD. The greater the initial weight increase, the greater the risk of developing congestive heart

failure. 3 kg weight growth in the first 6 weeks of exposure to atrasentan; it is possible that weight increase cutoffs might be stricter. 2nd, in the post hoc analysis of the phase IIB atrasentan trials, a decrease in eGFR was found to be predictive with greater weight gain in diabetic CKD patients. Pending post hoc examination of the SONAR data may reveal a lot of information on who is most at risk for fluid retention-related problems. Fifth, SONAR patients had stage 3B CKD and longstanding hyperglycemia, which increased the likelihood of fluid retention problems. In contrast, primary FSGS or IgA nephropathy may have limited clinically meaningful ETA receptor antagonist-induced fluid retention in younger individuals. Distinctly, ET receptor antagonist treatment may be titrated to the dosage that delivers the greatest proteinuria decrease while limiting fluid retention.

17. Conclusion

Pre-clinical research shows that the ET system is important for controlling renal function in health and illness. Essentially, every cell in the kidney generates and binds ET-1, which then results in a multitude of renal complications. A huge number of different stimuli activate the ET-1 pathway, which contributes to proteinuria, fibrosis, and inflammation. Although ET has been associated with the pathophysiology of a number of renal illnesses, just a few are included above.

Previous clinical studies using ET receptor antagonists in renal illness have generated favorable outcomes. Selective ETA antagonism has a strong antiproteinuric impact on people with DKD and FSGS. SONAR was able to establish that atrasentan had a pronounced protective impact on renal functional degradation, which was quite comparable to CREDENCE; adverse events associated with fluid retention, however, were more common in SONAR. Some ongoing trials use ET receptor antagonists for the treatment of kidney disease and several other disorders, such as IgA nephropathy, FSGS, and sickle cell disease. Emerging data from other kidney illnesses, such as Alport syndrome, indicates that ET receptor antagonists may be therapeutic for many other kidney illnesses.

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